

EFFECT OF ALKALOIDS 15-HYDROXYAZOMETHINE AND 15-ACETOXYAZOMETHINE ON CARDIOMYOCYTE SARCOLEMMAL Na^+ / Ca^{2+} - EXCHANGE SYSTEMS

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Introduction. Today, the most common among heart cashiers all over the world is considered to be a disease of cardiac arrhythmia. On the basis of the pathogenesis of this disease lies a violation of the electrophysiological properties of cardiomyocytes, which are responsible for the specificity of excitability, automatism and action potential. Therefore, in the modern concept of prevention and treatment of cardiac arrhythmias, the leading role is played by the creation of a new generation of antiarrhythmic means for the development of new approaches to the correction of these disorders.

A certain result was achieved by organizing research work aimed at the implementation of large-scale measures aimed at creating highly effective medicinal products from local raw materials in the Republic and providing the national pharmaceutical market with high-quality medicines. Separately, it should be noted that medicinal preparations from local raw materials (diterpenoid alkaloids from plants) are widely used in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases.

The aim of the study is to modulate the function of the Na^+ / Ca^{2+} -exchange system of the heart cell using 15-hydroxyazometin atizin (15-gaa) and 15-acetoxyazometin atizin (15 - aaa) diterpene alkaloids isolated from the plant species *Aconitum zeravshanicum*.

Material and techniques. In experiments, preparations of the papillary muscle of the rat heart were used as objects. White, breedless rats (200-250 g) were immobilized under the influence of diethyl ether, lifeless in the tservical dislocation method and opened the chest in a surgical manner. The heart was separated from the blood vessels and fixed to the container of the drug, in which the saline solution was filled. The Krebs saline solution used was prepared in the following composition (mm): NaCl-118; KCl-4.7; CaCl₂-2.5; MgSO₄-1.2; KH₂PO₄-1.1; glucose-5.5; NaHCO₃-25, pH-7.4. The heart was cut off from the middle part and the papillary muscle located in the right ventricle was separated. The average diameter of the papillary muscle drug is 0.4-0.8 mm, the length is 1-3 mm.ni makes up. The muscle preparation was fixed to the wall of the experimental chamber

(5 ml) using thread rings, and the mechanotron F30 (Hugo Satche, Germany) hook with the second end. Experiment chamber perfusion at a rate of 6 ml/min with Krebs solution, which is provided by aeration with gas containing O₂ (95%) and SO₂ (5%) Pt- the electrode was carried out using the papillary muscle drug contraction activity studied under isometric conditions, 60 min before the start of the experiment. In order for stable contraction activity and electrogenesis to occur in the muscle during, incubation was carried out using a current with a frequency of 0.1 Hz (at a duration of 5 MS). After incubation, the maximum isometric contraction length of the papillary muscle (L_{max}) was found, and all experiments were carried out under these conditions. With the help of the capillary muscle drug ESL-2 electrostimulator (Russia), the Bore was triggered by Pt-electrodes with a current force directed at an angle, its mechanical activity was transmitted through the ft30 mechanotron to the Tam-a (Germany) amplifier and recorded on a special paper through the line Recorder TZ 4620 (Czechoslovakia) samopise.

When performing the work, *Aconitum zeravshanicum* was isolated from the plant species, the alkaloids of the diterpene series – 15-acetoxiazometin atizin (4v-methyl-15v 15 - acetoxyatiz 16,17-en-N, 20-imin) and 15-hydroxyazometin atizin (4v-met).

The results obtained and their analysis. It is known that the negative inotropic effect of Class 1 antiarrhythmic agents is based on blocking the Na⁺-channels, which usually consists in reducing the penetration of Ca²⁺-ions into the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR), which is provided by the Na⁺/Ca²⁺-exchange system, as well as by it [1]. In cardiomyocytes, in the normal physiological state, the Na⁺ / Ca²⁺-exchange system is the main system that releases Na⁺ ions into the cell, releasing Ca²⁺ + ions outside the cell [2]. In addition, however, in nonphysiological cases, as a result of the operation of the Na⁺/Ca²⁺-exchange system in reverse mode, the penetration of Ca²⁺ ions inside the cell leads to an increase in the concentration of Ca²⁺ from the norm, and as a result of this, causes diseases that occur in the cardiovascular system [3; 4]. In our initial experiments, we observed that the rat heart of the alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa had clearly visible inotropic activity in the preparations of the papillary muscle. 15th gaa and 15th.

Initially, in our experiments, we examined the role of the Na⁺/Ca²⁺-exchange system located in the Cardiomyocyte

sarcolemma under the influence of the papillary muscle contraction activity of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa with the help of its blocker - KB-R7943. KB-R7943 blocks the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ - exchange system, weakening the contractile activity of the heart muscle as a result of a decrease in the amount of Ca^{2+} in cardiomyocytes [Ca^{2+}], and this process is reflected in the form of a negative inotropic effect [5]. In the experiment, it was found that when we observed the effect of KB-R7943 on the force of capillary muscle contraction, we reduced the dose-dependent effect by a maximum of $24.8 \pm 3.9\%$ compared to the control of muscle contraction force at a concentration of $30 \mu\text{M}$. Under these conditions, the semi-maximum impact concentration of KB-R7943 was $\text{ED}_{50} = 20.6 \pm 3.1 \mu\text{M}$, reducing the force of capillary muscle contraction by $50.0 \pm 4.5\%$ compared to control. In the environment KB-R7943 $20.6 \mu\text{M}$ under the existing conditions, the effect of concentration of 15 to $30 \mu\text{M}$ on the activity of capillary muscle contraction can be observed

Figure 1. Effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the activity of capillary muscle contraction $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ – exchange system blocker-KB-R7943 in existing conditions. On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$ ($n = 4-5$).

In order to add to and clarify our above experiments, cardiac glycoside-ouabain was used in our subsequent experiments to study the role of the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -exchange system in the effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the activity of capillary muscle contraction.

Ouabain inhibits $\text{Na}^+ / \text{K}^+ - \text{ATPase}$, causing an increase in Na^+ in cardiomyocyte, resulting in an increase in the contraction force of the papillary muscle due to increased penetration of Ca^{2+} ions into the cell through the $\text{Na}^+ / \text{Ca}^{2+}$ - exchange system [6;7]. It was observed that when we observed the effect of ouabain on the activity of capillary muscle contraction, it increased the contraction force at a concentration of $20 \mu\text{M}$ by $84.8 \pm 5.3\%$ compared to control (100% obtained) with a positive inotropic effect depending on the dose (Figure 2 A).

Figure 2. Dose-dependent effect of ouabain on the activity of capillary muscle contraction. Dose-dependent effect of α -ouabain on the activity of papillary muscle contraction without ishtrocos of nifedipine ($10 \mu\text{M}$), dose-dependent effect of β -ouabain on the

activity of papillary muscle contraction under conditions where nifedipine (10 μm) is present in the environment. On the ordinate axis- the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The concentration of Ouabain is expressed in (μm). The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$ ($n = 5$).

Also in the experiment, its blocker-nifedipine - was used in order to eliminate the entry of the Ca^{2+} -ion through the potential-dependent Ca^{2+} channel. When we observed the effect of ouabain (20 μm) in conditions where there is a concentration of nifedipine 10 μm in the medium, it was found that the force of capillary muscle contraction increases by $68.6 \pm 3.6\%$ (Figure 2 B). The contraction called ouabain in this case is only due to Ca^{2+} -ions entering through the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -exchange system. Under these conditions, the half-maximum concentration of 15-Haa was found to be reduced by $68.6 \pm 3.6\%$ to $31.1 \pm 3.3\%$, the maximum concentration to $6.9 \pm 3.1\%$ under the action of $\text{ED}_{50} = 8.7 \mu\text{m}$ (fig. Also in the experiment, it was found that 15-aaa also had a negative inotropic effect depending on the dose compared to the force of the capillary muscle contraction called using ouabain. The semi-maximum concentration of 15-AAA (ED_{50}) under the action of 16.7 μm using ouabain called capillary muscle contraction force from $68.6 \pm 3.6\%$

Figure 3. The effect of the alkaloid 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the force of capillary muscle contraction, called using ouabain. On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle, expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$ ($n = 5$).

According to the analysis of these results, we can trace the force of the capillary muscle contraction, called with the help of ouabain, to the reduction in the action of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa, with their effect on the reduction in the penetration of $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -ions into the cell through the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -exchange system.

In order to further clarify the above points, we checked the effect of the 15-gaa alkaloid on the force of capillary muscle contraction, which is called using ouabain, in the environment under the existing conditions of the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ -exchange system blocker – KB-R7943. In the experiment, when we observed the effects of 15-gaa (30 μM) and 15-aaa (30 μM) alkaloids under existing conditions $\text{ED}_{50} = 20.6 \mu\text{M}$, the semi-maximum concentration of KB-R7943 in the medium to the force of capillary muscle contraction called using ouabain, it was found that compared to existing conditions KB-R7943, the force of contraction

effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa on the force of capillary muscle contraction called by ouabain KB-R7943 in existing conditions. On the ordinate axis-the force of contraction of the papillary muscle,

expressed as a percentage in relation to control, was taken as 100%. The frequency of excitation of the drug is 0.5 Hz. In all cases, $p < 0.05$ ($n = 5$).

Based on the analysis of the results obtained, we can conclude that with the help of ouabain, the force of capillary muscle contraction, called KB-R7943 in the medium, there was an additional further decrease in the effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa, but it was found that this pointer is much less than the result obtained without the participation of KB-R7943. This data once again indicates that alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa interact with the Na^+/Ca^{2+} - exchange system, reducing the entry of Ca^{2+} ions through this system, and this process is reflected in the form of negative inotropic effects.

Conclusions

An important role in ensuring the negative inotropic effect of alkaloids 15-gaa and 15-aaa is played by the Na^+/Ca^{2+} -exchange system, the activation of which in conditions of neither Ca^{2+} - channel blockade and a decrease in the amount of Na^+ ions is due to the increased outflow of Ca^{2+} ions from cardiomyocytes. Usub confirms our opinion once again that their negative inotropic effect is further reduced when we observe the action of alkaloids by blocking Ca^{2+} -channels using nifedipine in the existing condition KB-R7943 in the mixture to the contraction called above using ouabain.

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